

Editorial

Introduction to the April special issues of the *International Journal of Language Studies on Language(ing), Multilingualism, Diversity, Equity, Social Justice, and Language Activism*

Chaka CHAKA, University of South Africa, South Africa¹

Thembeke SHANGE, University of South Africa, South Africa²

Sibusiso Clifford NDLANGAMANDLA, University of South Africa, South Africa³

Thulile SHANDU-PHETLA, University of South Africa, South Africa⁴

1. Introduction

Voices of linguistically heterogeneous and polycultural societies are increasingly being heard in the scholarly arena. Couched in these voices are calls for linguistic equity, social justice, and linguistic diversity. In most instances, these calls, themselves, have been accompanied by appeals for epistemological diversity, for the decolonial turn, and for the de-hegemonisation of language paradigms (Chaka, 2020, 2021, 2023a, 2024; Csata & Marácz, 2021; Ndlangamandla, 2024; Ndlangamandla & Chaka, 2022; Salmani Nodoushan, 2024). Invariably, one of the conduits for achieving social justice and linguistic diversity and for levelling the linguistic playing field is translanguaging. While it is not devoid of flaws and lacunae (see Chaka, 2023b; Jaspers, 2017) it is, nonetheless, one of the options that is currently preferred and embraced by many scholars.

2. Contents of the April special issue

The set of points mentioned above brings into sharp focus this second volume of the special issue, whose main theme is, *Language(ing), multilingualism, diversity, equity, social justice, and language activism*. The six papers comprising this volume speak to multilingualism and translanguaging and to social justice and linguistic diversity in varying degrees. For example, Ndlangamandla et al.'s paper investigates crosslinguistic and multimodal health communication strategies employed by the South African government during the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020-2022. The paper employs a multimodal critical discourse analysis (MCDA) to explore public health communication by government

¹ Corresponding Author: chakachaka8@gmail.com

² Corresponding Author: ezengetc@unisa.ac.za

³ Corresponding Author: CNdlanga@unisa.ac.za

⁴ Corresponding Author: shandtp@unisa.ac.za

officials in South Africa and by members of the National Coronavirus Command Council who were mandated to combat the spread of COVID-19 in South Africa. It interrogates how language and messaging limited or enabled linguistic equity and social justice. The paper concludes that in a country such as South Africa, for any government's initiative to promote linguistic and social justice, it ought to be 'language' and messaged through the linguistic repertoires that the majority of its citizens understand; if not, it is doomed to fail as was the case with the South African government's COVID-19 communication strategies.

The second paper, by Balosa, explores the way in which an existential sociolinguistic paradigm helps deconstruct the oppression and exclusion of minority or indigenous languages in multilingual societies in the Global North and in the Global South. It employs existential sociolinguistics as its theoretical framework and philosophical reflection to address the question: How can existential sociolinguistics foster existential justice in building more humane relations (BMHR) among languages within multilingual societies? It, then, argues that existential justice as an overarching justice encompasses all models of justice and should help promote an attitude of linguistic intercultural solidarity and a treatment of dignity towards all languages. The paper concludes that laws and policies about languages in modern multilingual societies need to overcome econotechnocracy, that is, a world order in which economic and technological powers subordinate justice, democracy, and the legitimacy of less-powerful nations, cultures, and languages.

The paper by Salmani Nodoushan entitled "Language colonization or lingua franca? Demystifying the status quo of Persian" draws on the existing literature from diverse fields including biology, history, developmental psychology, and sociolinguistics to defy historical myths about Persian and to defend the current status of this language. It argues that Persian is the pedigree 'lingua franca' of communication in Iran, is learnt as a mother tongue by all Iranian citizens, and is spoken by all Iranian citizens who belong to a rich variety of pedigree-Iranian cultural populations that encompass Gilak, Mazandarani, Baloch, Azerbaijani, Turkmen, Qashqai, Assyrian, Armenian, Lur, Talysh, Tat, and so on. The paper does not deny that there are random political dissidents who desperately desire to sell their 'myth' that Persian has long been a colonizing force, yet it argues that the vast majority of Iranians earnestly argue that Persian has never been a colonizing language. It emphasizes that the majority Iranian group argues that Persian has historically been a lingua franca or a language of communication freely and consciously chosen by 'pedigree' inhabitants of the Iranian plateau who have cherished it throughout history. Salmani Nodoushan's paper (a) draws on the existing literature on 'language colonization' and 'language weaponization' to afford a clear understanding of these topics and (b) aims at demystifying the status quo of Persian. It follows a line of argumentation that shows why what it calls the 'myth propagated by the

random political dissidents' is invalid. It concludes that Persian has never been a colonizing force and argues that the 'teaching *of* local languages' is quite acceptable, but 'teaching *in* local languages' is the call the call by radical separatist groups who aim at the disintegration of the historically-unified nation of Iran.

The fourth paper, entitled, "Linguistic diversity in institutional collections: Beyond preservation to valorisation," is by Hannaford and Alexander. It starts off by stating a well-documented view that language has the capacity to influence and perpetuate ideologies, cultural values, and social conditions. From this standpoint, the paper argues that fighting against linguistic prejudice and promoting language equity are crucial to contemporary cultural concerns around challenging prescriptivist worldviews and disrupting hegemonic historical perspectives. It sees institutional collections as representing promising staging grounds for such efforts, with wide reach and accessibility, but as typically focused on, and curated in, mainstream language varieties. The paper, then, sets out to explore how institutional collections may correct this homogeneity, through connecting materials containing regional/social language varieties, including those of community archives, into collections more representative of diverse linguistic and cultural landscapes. Utilising an AHRC-funded project integrating community-generated content into the UK national collection as example, the paper addresses challenges and makes recommendations for effectively valorising language varieties in institutional collections. Finally, as a consequence, the paper argues for the potential of linguistically diverse institutional collections as transformative tools for promoting language equity and reducing linguistic prejudice.

Huang's paper, entitled, "Language loss and translanguaging identities near the Navajo land", explores Navajo students' claim that they do not speak the Navajo language fluently. The data used in the paper was collected through background forms and in-class writing exercises. The paper makes a number of observations. Firstly, a minority of the Navajo students claimed that they can hold a conversation or get by with another Navajo speaker in Navajo. Secondly, some of the students asserted that their parents never or hardly ever spoke Navajo to them, so they never learned the language. Thirdly, other students averred that only their grandparents spoke Navajo to them. As a result, these students lost their Navajo language proficiency because their parents, as opposed to their grandparents, never spoke the language to them. Fourthly, still, the other students claimed that their grandparents passed away, and this led to their losing their Navajo language proficiency. Fifthly and finally, the majority of the Navajo students hope to learn or re-learn Navajo, which is their heritage language.

The rise of technomultilingualism for language equity and social justice through subtitling and eye-tracking is what Kruger-Marais' paper is about. It investigates the cognitive effectiveness of watching subtitled discipline-specific videos to determine how subtitling, as an emerging technology, encourages language equity and also social justice as well as the rise of technomultilingualism. It examines cognitive effectiveness by using gaze duration eye-tracking as a proxy for attention allocation and for gist comprehension together with scene and word recognition. The paper uses eye-tracking data from seven student participants in the Faculty of Natural and Agricultural Sciences at the University of Pretoria. The students were offered subtitles in English, Afrikaans, isiZulu, and Sepedi. However, the participants who volunteered for the study selected largely English and Afrikaans subtitles, and the isiZulu and Sepedi subtitles were unfortunately not utilised during this particular study. The paper concludes that the participants preferred English subtitles and remembered certain concepts from the videos better when their focus was on the subtitles themselves rather than exclusively on the on-screen image.

The Authors

Chaka Chaka (Email: chakachaka8@gmail.com) is a professor of applied English language studies in the Department of English Studies at the University of South Africa (UNISA). His research interests include the following areas: language studies, language and decoloniality, language and education, literacies, computer-mediated communication (CMC), electronic learning (e-learning), computer assisted language learning (CALL), mobile learning (m-learning), mobile assisted language learning (MALL), and technology-enhanced learning.

Thembeke Shange (Email: ezengetc@unisa.ac.za) has worked as an academic development practitioner in the Student Development and Support Directorate at the Tshwane University of Technology (TUT) for 15 years. Currently, she is a senior lecturer in English Studies at the University of South Africa (UNISA). Her research interests are: computer assisted language learning, applied English language studies, multilingualism, multimodality, ESL, critical literacy, multiliteracies, discourse analysis, and ODeL, to name a few.

Sibusiso C. Ndlangamandla (Email: cndlanga@unisa.ac.za) is a senior lecturer in the Department of English Studies at the University of South Africa (UNISA). His research focuses on sociolinguistics, computer-mediated communication, multilingualism, multimodality, language policy, and online teaching and learning in higher education. His location in open distance elearning (ODeL) has made him focus on applied linguistics and technology, Southern theories, decolonization, social justice, Africanization, integrational linguistics, TESOL,

academic literacies, discourse analysis, and the hegemony of the English Language in South Africa and the globe, among others.

Thuli Shandu-Phetla (Email: shandtp@unisa.ac.za) has been in the Department of English Studies at the University of South Africa (UNISA) for over 20 years. She was recently appointed as chair of the department (CoD). Her research interests are in ODL, applied English language studies, technology assisted language learning, multilingualism, and multimodality. She is passionate about the varied facets of student support.

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